

Sustainability Best Practices Manual

D8.3

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Authors (Organisation): Deitze Otaduy
(University of Deusto)

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Meaning
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
GPP	Green Public Procurement
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
KPI	Key Impact Parameters
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
QoC	Quality of Consumption
SBP	Sustainability Best Practices
SC	Sustainability Committee
SC	Sustainability Committee
UN	United Nations

1 Executive Summary

If food loss and waste (FLW) were a country, it would be the third leading cause of greenhouse gas emissions. FLW also burdens waste management systems and exacerbates food insecurity, contributing significantly to the three global crises of climate change, nature and biodiversity loss, and pollution and waste.

PRECIOUS, a transdisciplinary alliance of 18 entities from 11 EU countries, believes that reliable data on the environmental impacts of FLW is crucial for accelerating EU progress towards climate targets and reducing environmental impacts (including biodiversity) across the food supply chain. The project's collective understanding is that the challenge goes beyond measuring the amount of food saved or CO₂ emissions. When food is wasted, valuable and limited resources such as water, land use, and energy are lost, while 8.9% of the worldwide population is suffering from hunger according to FAO, therefore, depleting the planet's natural resources. It is critical to broaden our understanding of the issue to transform the food system and raise public awareness that motivates change.

PRECIOUS aims to contribute to the transformation of food systems by addressing existing data gaps and developing a unified and openly accessible evaluation framework to quantify the economic, environmental, and social impacts of strategies to reduce FLW, considering potential rebound effects.

The project will engage stakeholders from 2 Use Cases (Spain and Greece) and 3 Co-creation and Replication Nodes (Poland, Lithuania, Hungary) to address systemic causes across geographical boundaries. The project aims to induce a fundamental change in attitudes and behaviours towards food consumption and disposal through collaborative efforts and innovative methods, fostering a more just and sustainable EU food system.

As indicated in section 2.2-Management figures, of deliverable D8.1, Quality Management Plan, a committee, the Sustainability Committee (SC), has been designed to ensure all partners are involved and planned measures are implemented. The SC formed by UD, as coordinator, and E3M, as an expert in sustainability, will verify that the products, processes, transport, and infrastructure developed by the project result in a net reduction in environmental impacts following the DNSH bases. To collect the best practices to reduce the detrimental environmental and climate impacts that the project may have, the SC has prepared this deliverable, **D8.3 - sustainability best practices manual**: plan and conclusions on the sustainable practices' management of the project. It was created at the project's onset to assess the current condition and identify necessary measures.

This deliverable outlines the framework and guidelines adopted by the PRECIOUS consortium to ensure sustainability through green procurement practices, environmentally friendly actions, and directives for organizing events, travelling, and managing dissemination and communication materials. These measures align with the European Green Deal, Horizon Europe's sustainability requirements, and broader global environmental goals. In addition, D8.3 aims to guide the consortium in organizing sustainable events and travel, promote eco-friendly approaches to dissemination and communication, standardize compliance with EU green directives and provide tools to evaluate and enhance sustainability.

Moreover, this deliverable will be updated throughout the project, identifying new arising environmental risks and how to prevent and minimize them. At the end of the project, this report will also collect the lessons learnt. Therefore, a set of KPIs (section 5) will be assigned to monitor its proper execution.

2 Introduction

Sustainability is at the core of the PRECIOUS mission. The main objective of this “Sustainability best practices manual” is to follow Green Management, that is, to implement measures to reduce the environmental impact of the project itself, for example, using Green Public Procurement (GPP), environmental management systems, etc. Thus, deliverable D8.3 integrates key directives and strategies to: minimize the project’s environmental footprint, ensure sustainable approaches to events, travel, dissemination, promote eco-friendly approaches to dissemination and communication, standardize compliance with EU green directives and provide tools to evaluate and enhance sustainability.

Finally, certain Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be established to demonstrate that all consortium partners and the coordinator are in alignment with the implementation of the GPP strategy at all stages of the project.

This document reflects the Sustainability Best Practices (SBP) to be followed during the implementation of the PRECIOUS project. This strategy is adapted to the guidelines set by the European Commission (EC) by seeking to procure goods, services and works with a reduced environmental impact during their life cycle, compared to other goods, services and works with the same primary function that would be procured instead.

This approach responds to the global need to minimize the detrimental environmental impacts caused by socio-economic development and industrial activity, for which a balance should be found between the latter and the protection of resources. This sustainability challenge affects governments, industries, communities and individuals, all of whom can contribute by applying the principles of Quality of Consumption (QoC) in their consumption decisions. Firstly, it helps to reduce the environmental impact by saving energy and material resources and reducing the concentration of pollutants and greenhouse emissions. Secondly, it reduces costs by purchasing low-maintenance and more durable products, as well as reducing the amount of waste generated. Finally, it has an important effect on environmental awareness, as well as being exemplary. As stated in [the Green Paper on Integrated Product Policy](#), the demand for such products - has to be generated and reinforced through a process of mutual education between companies, which should actively promote environmental information, and consumers, who should challenge companies to improve the environmental characteristics of their products - is a significant tool for the achievement of environmental policy objectives related to climate change, biodiversity preservation, resource use and sustainable production and consumption.

The GPP Strategy of the PRECIOUS project will involve identifying and selecting environmentally preferable offers during project implementation, considering environmental aspects as well as sustainability of production processes or life cycle costing. In addition, simple and effective methods of "greening" contracts will be examined.

In this way, the PRECIOUS project will contribute to the achievement of local, regional, national and international sustainability objectives by providing other companies with real incentives to develop environmentally friendly products and services. The implementation of the strategy described in this document will allow significant economic savings to the partners involved through the purchase of energy efficient products, the reduction of hazardous substances in the products purchased (which will reduce the costs associated with their disposal) or the use of reusable products (reduction in the use of raw materials) and will facilitate meeting the current environmental challenges through the minimization of greenhouse gas and pollutant emissions and proper waste management, moving towards a circular economy model.

3 Legal Framework

For the implementation of this SBP strategy in the PRECIOUS project, the following regulations will be mainly taken into account during all activities related to project implementation:

- EU Green Public Procurement (GPP): Align procurement activities with EU GPP criteria to support green suppliers.
- European Green Deal Objectives: Integrate sustainability metrics into all project operations.
- [Energy Efficiency Directive – recast](#) (EU/2023/1791)
- [Delegated regulation on the first phase of the establishment of a common Union rating scheme for data centres](#) (EU/2024/1364)
- Communication – [REPowerEU Plan](#) (COM/2022/230)
- Communication – [EU "Save Energy"](#) (COM/2022/240)
- [Energy efficiency targets](#)
- [Renewable Energy Directive](#) EU/2023/2413
- [Revised Clean Vehicles Directive \(2019/1161\)](#)
- Directive 2009/33/EC on the promotion of clean and energy efficient road transport vehicles.
- Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH).
 - The REACH Regulation initially made no specific provision for nanomaterials. In 2018 the Commission adopted [Commission Regulation \(EU\) 2018/1881](#) to modify REACH technical Annexes I, III and VI-XII, introducing nano-specific clarifications and provisions. In 2020 the Commission also updated Annex II with [Commission Regulation \(EU\) 2020/878](#), introducing new provisions on Safety Data Sheets to complement the new registration requirements for nanomaterials.
- [Directive \(EU\) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.](#)
- Directive 2009/28/EC on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.
- Directive 2008/98/EC on waste (Waste Framework Directive).
- [Directive \(EU\) 2018/851 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste \(Text with EEA relevance\)](#)
- Communication from the Commission Closing the loop: An EU action plan for the circular economy. COM/2015/0614 final).
- State Waste Management Framework Plan (PEMAR) 2016-2022.
- [Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive \(CSDDD\)](#) - Directive (EU) 2024/1760: Adopted in 2024, this directive requires companies to identify and address adverse human rights and environmental impacts in their operations and value chains. It aims to foster sustainable and responsible corporate behavior.
- [ISO 20400:2017 Sustainable Procurement](#) – Guidance: Although not a regulation, this international standard provides guidance on integrating sustainability into procurement processes, complementing existing EU directives and regulations.
- [Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive \(CSRD\)](#)
- GRI Standards Guidelines: Ensure GRI disclosure requirements are met for all relevant indicators.
- ISO 14001 Compliance: Ensure suppliers adhere to recognised environmental management standards.

More information can be found in the EU Environment Policies and Regulations (<https://wecoop.eu/regional-knowledge-centre/eu-policies-regulations/>).

4 PRECIOUS Sustainability Best Practices Plan

The PRECIOUS Consortium remains committed to sustainability through proactive green procurement and environmentally friendly actions. The strategies outlined in this document will ensure that the project contributes positively to EU sustainability goals.

When identifying categories for sustainable procurement within the PRECIOUS Horizon Europe project, several criteria are considered to prioritize efforts and resources effectively (Figure 1). These criteria ensure that procurement strategies align with the program's objectives and maximize their environmental, social, and economic impact, including:

1. Environmental and Social Impacts

Focus on categories with clear and significant environmental or social impacts, such as high resource consumption, hazardous material usage, or labour rights concerns.

2. Green alternatives

Include environmental criteria in tenders to prioritize suppliers with sustainable practices
 Prioritize categories with readily available sustainable alternatives that meet the project needs.

3. Sustainable Pricing for Cost-Effective Transitions

Sustainable pricing balances product costs with environmental and social impacts, ensuring prices reflect eco-friendly practices like sustainable materials and energy efficiency, while focusing on cost parity with conventional options to facilitate seamless, financially viable adoption

4. Local Sourcing

Choose local suppliers to reduce transportation emissions, supporting local economic development in the surrounding community.

5. Supplier Screening

Require suppliers to demonstrate compliance with environmental standards (e.g., ISO 14001).
 Prioritize goods and services with recognised eco-labels or certifications (e.g., EU Ecolabel, FSC, ENERGY STAR), which provide a standardised means of evaluating sustainability performance.
 In the absence of eco-labels, prioritize products meeting internationally recognised sustainability standards. Use globally accepted benchmarks for evaluating sustainability goals.

Figure 1. Criteria for Selecting Categories for Sustainable Procurement¹

In particular, the PRECIOUS SBP plan is based on the following criteria:

1. At Consortium level
 - a. All the entities engaged in the project are committed to using current excessive inventory materials instead of unnecessary stock materials or assets.
 - b. Consortium will minimize unnecessary movements of people and travelling, materials and assets to reduce the associated environmental impact and greenhouse gas emissions
 - c. All the participant entities (partners and stakeholders) will be aware of and apply when possible the ISO14000 best practices for waste materials management

¹ Source <https://empoweringcpo.com/sustainable-procurement/>

- d. The consortium will prioritize possible suppliers or stakeholders with competence in green product design, ISO14001 certification, and other related areas.
 - e. UD will lead and train all the participants in green process management principles regarding life cycle assessment, pollution prevention and reduction, design for the environment, etc.
 - f. The consortium is committed to applying strict control and prevention in technological processes with uncertainties about the associated environmental impact.
 - g. Green criteria will be considered a priority in the acquisition of new equipment (e.g., energy and water consumption, direct and indirect CO2 emissions)
 - h. 100% of the staff working in the framework of the PRECIOUS project will be aware of this SBP manual, read this deliverable and adhere to the PRECIOUS SBP.
2. At ecosystem level
- a. The consortium will prioritize potential suppliers or stakeholders with expertise in green product design, especially requiring that they meet the ISO14001 certificate best practices, etc.
 - b. Cross-cutting issues such as eco-design, green packaging, using less production transportation, etc. will be included in all the practical workshops. This learning content will be shared among all the stakeholders involved.
 - c. Stakeholders will be grouped around the locations where the project solutions are replicated to reduce logistics costs and travelling, thus reducing greenhouse gas emissions and air pollutants.
 - d. Special attention will be paid to stakeholders that can enrich the quality of the supply chain management with corporate social responsibility or upgrade the environmental management systems.
 - e. The consortium will keep in touch with regional governments and municipalities (especially in the pilot regions of the project) not only to disseminate the project results but also to discuss the ecology regulatory and supporting schemes that can foster the implementation of new green technologies.

4.1 SBP Plan at consortium level

Within the technical part of the project, further GPP can be applied. Taking primarily into account the EU Commission's "GPP-Collection of good practice" brochure and the "GPP toolkit- module", the principles will be applied.

If possible, the official EU GPP criteria will be followed as established by the Communication "Public Procurement for a better environment" (COM (2008) 400) and published periodically. If no defined criteria are available, the general GPP Good Practice will be followed. This will include the best offer in terms of environmental impacts, cost, time requested and years of experience. This would also ensure the maximum impact of the project from an environmental and overall sustainability perspective. Therefore, the environmental criteria and principles will follow the main objective of the project to decrease the environmental impact.

The consortium is aware of the global benefits of Green Procurement and is committed to adopting sustainable, cost-effective and energy efficient practices during the project implementation in all project related activities. To meet this objective, in addition to the aforementioned actions. The SC will direct and instruct all participants on green process management principles pertaining to environmental design.

Therefore, the following actions will be taken by the consortium staff and stakeholders involved in the project concerning the principles of GPP during the lifetime of the project:

Sustainable Travel Practices**Virtual Alternatives:**

- Prioritize online meetings, workshops, and webinars to reduce travel needs.
- Use hybrid formats for major events to limit participant travel.

Transport Choices:

- The Consortium will limit unneeded movements of people, materials, and assets in order to lessen the environmental effect of this commuting.
 - Conduct at least 70% of project meetings and stakeholder workshops in a non-face-to-face manner (via Google Meet or other online meeting apps like ZOOM or Teams).
 - Make at least 50% of journeys by public transport to minimize greenhouse gas emissions with a clear preference to avoid aviation trips when there is a good low-carbon alternative (i.e. high-speed rail) without a high time penalty.
 - Stakeholders will be grouped close to the project activities location to minimize logistical and travelling costs and associated greenhouse gas emissions.
- Encourage the use of trains or buses for regional travel over flights.
- If air travel is unavoidable, prioritize direct flights and economy class to reduce emissions.
- Promote carpooling or ride-sharing for local commutes.

Mobility Carbon Footprint Reduction:

- Offset emissions through verified carbon offset programs when travel is unavoidable.

To reduce the detrimental effects of transport, the staff, and stakeholders involved in the project will minimize “attended in person” or “face-to-face meetings” reducing CO₂ emissions and air pollution due to the transport. If an in-person meeting is necessary, the selected country and venue should be easily accessible. Ideally, there should be a direct connection, preferably by train, for all project participants. However, if the meeting involves a site of significant interest to the project—such as a use case where a visit holds real relevance—this guideline will be adjusted. In addition, the number of participants must be kept to the minimum necessary. The use of calls, video calls, emails, and a website intranet will replace the “face-to-face meetings” as much as possible and the remittance of documents by mail or messenger service. Furthermore, all required visual information (e.g. pilot installations) will be exchanged-diffused by video mail, as a priority.

If possible, technical meetings arising for the design and implementation of the PRECIOUS pilots will be attended by phone and conference. In any case, the number of travellers will be carefully controlled during the project implementation. Additionally, the selection criterion of transportation will be the least polluting transport, with a clear preference for public transport when possible.

When travelling by car is unavoidable, sharing cars will be preferred. When it is necessary to rent vehicles, criteria such as low noise, low energy consumption and, if possible, use of alternative or renewable fuels (especially electric vehicles) should be considered.

Sustainable Event Organization

To ensure all project-related events minimize environmental impact:

Venue Selection:

- Use eco-certified venues (e.g., ISO 20121-certified locations).
- Choose venues accessible by public transportation to minimize attendee emissions. However, if the meeting is celebrated in a site of high interest to the project, such as a use case where a visit is of real relevance to the project, this recommendation will be adjusted accordingly.

Catering:

- Prioritize plant-based menus, organic products, and local suppliers.
- Minimize food waste by estimating attendee numbers accurately.
- Use reusable or compostable dishes and cutlery.
- If possible, select food providers with FLW prevention strategies and that preferentially use local or proximity products

Energy Management:

- Optimize lighting, heating, and air conditioning.
- Use renewable energy sources when possible.

Waste Reduction:

- Implement a "zero-waste" policy with accessible recycling stations.
- Provide digital event materials instead of printed brochures.

Eco-Friendly Dissemination and Communication

Whenever feasible, eco-design, green packaging and reduced manufacturing transportation shall be addressed.

Materials:

- Use recycled or FSC-certified paper for necessary printed materials.
- Opt for biodegradable or reusable promotional items (e.g., cloth bags, bamboo pens).
- Avoid single-use plastics in giveaways.

Digital Communication:

To ensure sustainability, priority should be given to online dissemination and communication methods rather than paper-based materials such as flyers. Digital channels not only reduce environmental impact but also enhance accessibility, reach, and efficiency in information sharing.

- Host websites and online platforms on energy-efficient servers.
- Optimise digital content for faster loading and reduced energy consumption.
- Use email campaigns instead of printed newsletters.
- Use social media and online platforms to communicate about project results instead of printed media.

Events and Campaigns:

- Promote online dissemination strategies (social media, webinars).
- Use QR codes or NFC tags to share digital resources at events.
- Minimise poster production; use modular or reusable displays.

Paper Carbon Footprint Reduction.

PRECIOUS will foster the use of electronic devices to support information production and exchange. The use of paper and printing will be avoided when possible within project management. In addition, when printing documents is absolutely necessary (not-colour, double side and duplex) the paper used will follow the markings on the guidelines for innovative public procurement (Copying and graphic paper EU GPP criteria), which in turn are based on the criteria of eco-labels European Ecolabel, the Nordic Swan label and the Blue Angel label.

- Recycled paper shall be purchased whenever possible. When this is not possible, the paper that contains the greatest number of fibers from used paper, as well as paper without chlorinated compounds, shall be chosen. To this end, papers certified by an entity with officially recognised labels, such as the European eco-label, the AENOR mark, IPE eco-label, etc., shall be chosen.

- Suppliers will be requested to provide their products with reusable packaging. Batch sizes purchased will be optimised to minimise waste.
- Preference will be given to the purchase of recycled paper pads, notepads, envelopes, post-it notes, etc. and, in general, priority will be given to the purchase of products made from recycled materials and bearing eco-labels.
- Recycled paper will be used for the production of various materials for distribution in the dissemination and communication activities of the PRECIOUS project.
- Digital storage of information, ideally on cloud-based platforms, to enhance sustainability and accessibility. Cloud storage ensures secure, long-term archiving while reducing reliance on physical media such as CDs, memory sticks, and USB drives. This approach facilitates seamless documentation transfer, improves collaboration, and supports environmentally friendly practices by minimizing paper-based archiving.
- To minimise paper consumption, the printing of documents will be optimised and use will be made of e-mail and other computer networks for internal communication between units.

Consumables, equipment and infrastructures

- Existing inventory materials shall be utilised wherever possible instead of acquiring unneeded stock materials or assets.
- To apply the best value for money and Fairness principle for everything purchased for and within the project.
- To use recyclable or recycled materials and products whenever possible.
- To reduce the volume of packaging for all purchased products.
- Sustainable procurement will be encouraged by favouring local subcontractors and ISO certification, being the tools provided by the European Commission. Green procurement criteria will be used in the supply of generic materials (like paper and small IT equipment) and services (transport, catering of events, etc.). Sustainable requirements will be demanded complying with Environment Standard ISO 14001, Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS) and others related.

5 Monitoring Mechanism

The monitoring plan will help determine whether targets were met, identify challenges and opportunities, develop solutions and identify financial and resource savings.

For monitoring this strategy, a series of indicators are established that will be measured periodically to evaluate the progress of implementing the plan and fulfilling the objectives set (Table 1). The indicators measure procurement that has followed green purchasing criteria versus those that have not. In addition, corrective measures will be implemented in time to minimize any possible deviations.

At this early stage of project development, a preliminary set of KPIs has been defined, recognizing that the project's full requirements and the feasibility of monitoring all KPIs are not yet fully determined. Consequently, in future updates of the deliverable, the list of KPIs presented in Table 1 may be revised, with some indicators being added or removed as emerging project needs are identified. Furthermore, KPI monitoring procedures will be defined as a guideline for all partners to facilitate and establish common criteria for the correct monitoring of KPIs and the identification of potential deviations.

Table 1. Indicators for monitoring the SBP strategy

Indicator	Ratio	Periodicity
Transport		
Online meetings vs. Face-to-face	At least 80/20	Reporting Period
Use of train, bus vs plane for travel	At least 50/50	Reporting Period
Shared vs. individual car use	At least 90/20	Reporting Period
Materials		
Purchase of recycled paper or recycled media	At least 80%	Reporting Period
Online dissemination and (e.g., Social Media, digital reports, emails) over paper-based materials (e.g., flyers)	At least 80%	Reporting Period
Digital storage of information, ideally on cloud-based platforms to ensures secure, long-term archiving and minimize physical media use	At least 80%	Throughout the project and beyond
Use of paper and cardboard of recycled origin or with low chlorine content.	At least 80%	Throughout the project and beyond
General		
Staff working under the PRECIOUS project will be aware of the SBP manual, have read this deliverable and adhere to the PRECIOUS SBP.	100%	Throughout the project and beyond
Integration of sustainability considerations in procurement and purchasing decisions. Follow sustainability guidelines whenever possible	100% of awareness	Throughout the project and beyond

Indicator	Measure
Events organization	
No food waste	Plan the meeting having the exact number of attendees and the special dietary needs. If there is any food left over, either it will be offered internally at the event location, or an agreement will be reached to donate it to a nearby NGO or Tupperware will be provided to the attendees so that they can take the leftovers
Reusable name tags	Use of Flexible Printable Name Tags, Reusable for multi-day events
Elimination of single-use plastics	Avoid plastic badge holders and replace them with sustainable alternatives. No individual plastic water bottles will be provided; instead, large glass bottles with reusable glasses will be used. All cutlery will be reusable.
Sustainable promotional materials	Preferably digital event materials (e.g., QR codes, e-brochures) over printed handouts. Any printed materials should use recycled or eco-certified paper.
Sustainable venue selection	Prioritize venues with sustainability certifications (e.g., energy-efficient buildings, waste reduction policies).
Eco-friendly catering	Prioritize locally sourced, seasonal, and vegetarian/vegan-friendly food options.

5.1 Global Reporting Initiative – GRI

Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) [GRI - Home \(globalreporting.org\)](https://www.globalreporting.org) offers the most comprehensive set of sustainability reporting standards that cover economic, environmental and social impacts.

Through their activities and business relationships, organizations can affect the economy, environment, and people, and, in turn, make negative or positive contributions to sustainable development. Sustainable development refers to ‘development which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs’². The objective of sustainability reporting using the GRI Sustainability Reporting Standards (GRI Standards) is to provide transparency on how an organization contributes or aims to contribute to sustainable development.

The GRI Standards enable an organization to publicly disclose its most significant impacts on the economy, environment, and people, including its impacts on human rights and how it manages these impacts. This enhances transparency of the organization’s impacts and increases organizational accountability.

The Standards contain disclosures that allow an organization to report information about its impacts consistently and credibly. This enhances the global comparability and quality of reported information on these impacts, which supports information users in making informed assessments and decisions about the organization’s impacts and contribution to sustainable development.

The GRI Standards are based on expectations for responsible business conduct set out in authoritative intergovernmental instruments, such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises [3] and the United Nations (UN) Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights [5] (see the Bibliographies of the GRI Standards for a list of authoritative instruments used in developing the GRI Standards). Information reported using the GRI Standards can help users assess whether an

² Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies (EiE) Glossary Term - [Sustainable development](#)

organization meets the expectations set out in these instruments. It is important to note that the GRI Standards do not set allocations, thresholds, goals, targets, or any other benchmarks for good or bad performance.

5.1.1 GRI Standards for PRECIOUS implementation

In alignment with GRI Standards the project will use the following GRI Standards for reviewing the project performance:

Materials (GRI 301)

- Evaluate the use of recycled or sustainably sourced materials in procurement and communication.
- Track reductions in paper and plastic use.

Energy (GRI 302)

- Measure energy consumption from project-related events, facilities, and digital platforms (when data is available).
- Report on the share of renewable energy used.

Emissions (GRI 305)

- Quantify carbon emissions from travel and events.
- Disclose mitigation measures, including carbon offset programs and sustainable transport choices.

Waste (GRI 306)

- Report on the waste generated and the percentage of waste recycled or composted.
- Track reductions in single-use plastics and other non-recyclable materials.

Supplier Environmental Assessment (GRI 308)

- Evaluate suppliers based on their adherence to environmental standards, such as ISO 14001.
- Report on the percentage of green-certified suppliers.

These GRI standards can also be related to PRECIOUS environmentally Friendly Actions as described below:

Sustainable Event Organization

- Monitor emissions from venue energy use and attendee travel (GRI 305)
- Implement zero-waste policies with clear metrics for waste reduction and recycling (GRI 306)

Sustainable Travel Practices

- Track energy consumption and emissions from all project-related travel (GRI 302 & 305)
- Encourage low-carbon travel options (e.g., trains, carpooling) and measure their impact (GRI 305)

Eco-Friendly Dissemination and Communication

- Quantify the use of recycled materials in printed outputs (GRI 301 & 306)
- Assess the energy efficiency of digital dissemination platforms (GRI 302)

Several examples can be found on the GRI website: Standards per language - GRI - Download the Standards ([globalreporting.org](https://www.globalreporting.org)), [GRI - Download the Standards \(globalreporting.org\)](https://www.globalreporting.org)

6 References

[Green Paper on Integrated Product Policy](#)

EU Environment Policies and Regulations

(<https://wecoop.eu/regional-knowledge-centre/eu-policies-regulations/>).

